

ICCM22

Ultra-High-Molecular-Weight Polyethylene (UHMWPE) as Space Radiation and Hypervelocity Impact Shielding Material for Low Earth Orbit Space Structures

Ji-Hun Cha

Professor: Chun-Gon Kim

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Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology, (KAIST)

Smart Structures and Composites Lab

1. Introduction
 - Background
 - Objective and Scope

2. Space Radiation Characteristics of UHMWPE
 - Proton Irradiation

3. Hypervelocity Impact Resistance of UHMWPE
 - Fabric Impact Energy Absorption

4. Conclusion

1.1 Space Environment

< Low Earth Orbit space debris >

LEO space environment [1]

Proton	0.1 ~ 400MeV
Electron	0.04 ~ 4.5MeV
Heavy ion	0.1 ~ 100MeV
Space debris	7 ~ 15 km/s
Thermal cycling	-150 ~ 150 °C

<Space radiation types in LEO[2]>

1.2 Space Structural Configuration

[1]YunHo Kim, Chunghyeon Choi, Hypervelocity impact on flexible curable composites and pure fabric layer bumpers for inflatable space structures, Volume 176(15), pp 1061-1072, 2017.
 [2] John H, "Integrated Multilayer Insulation", NASA Tech Brief, 2009.
 [3]R. Destefanis, E. Amerio, M. Briccarello, SPACE ENVIRONMENT CHARACTERISATION OF KEVLAR: GOOD FOR BULLETS, DEBRIS AND RADIATION TOO, 2010.
 [4]Graves, Russell(Boeing Co., Houston, TX, United States), International Space Station: Meteoroid/Orbital Debris Survivability and Vulnerability, NASA Johnson Space Center, 2000.
 [5]A.M.Jorgensen, S.E.Patamiab, B.Gassend, Passive radiation shielding considerations for the proposed space elevator, Acta Astronautica, Volume 60, Issue 3, Pages 198-209, 2007.

< Creation of debris cloud >

	Front bumper ^[1]	MLI ^[2]	Middle bumper ^[3]	Primary structure ^[4]
Characteristic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creation of debris cloud - Space environment resistance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduction of solar radiation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Blocks debris cloud - No structural function 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Main structural function
Typical material	Aluminum	Mylar + Kapton foil	Nextel + Kevlar fabric	Aluminum

→ Space radiation shielding is considered unimportant to conventional space structures^[5]

1.3 Effects of Space Radiation on Human and Spacecraft

Dose(rem)	ISS residence	Symptoms ^[1]
50 ~ 100	3 ~ 5 year	10% radiation sickness
150 ~ 200	7 ~ 10 year	50% radiation sickness
350 ~ 550	17 ~ 27 year	50% deaths

Electronic device problems^[2]

Single Event Effect(SEE)	High-energy proton pass through the semiconductor
Total Ionizing Dose(TID)	Accumulation of radiation

Spacecraft problems^[3]

Hubble Space Telescope(1990)	Guidance system, Telescope status monitors, failed because of radiation.
Telstar401 (1997)	Circuit breakdown with solar flare proton.

1.4 Space Radiation Shielding Mechanism

Proton and heavy ion shielding

- BETHE equation^[1].

$$\text{Stopping power: } -\frac{dE}{dx} = \frac{4\pi(z_p)^2}{m_e v^2} \times \left(\frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0}\right)^2 \times \left(\frac{N_A Z \rho}{M_u A}\right) \times \ln\left(\frac{2m_e v^2}{10 Z}\right)$$

z_p : Particle atomic number (Proton : $z = 1$, Fe ion : $z = 26$)

Z : Material atomic number, A : Relative atomic mass

v : Particle with speed, E : Energy, X : Shielding distance, ϵ_0 : Vacuum permittivity, e : Electron charge, m_e : Electron mass, ρ : Density of material, M_u : Molar mass constant, N_A : Avogadro number

Most effective element is hydrogen.

- $(Z/A)_H = 1/1.008$, $(Z/A)_{Fe} = 26/55.845$

<Proton shielding effect by elements [2]>

[1] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bethe_formula

[2] W.C. Fan, C.R. Drumm, S.B. Roeske, G.J. Scrivner, 1996, Shielding considerations for satellite microelectronics, IEEE Nuclear and Plasma Sciences Society.

1.5 Space Radiation Shielding and Bulletproof Performance of UHMWPE

- **Space radiation shielding of PE**
- Hydrogen-rich PE would be effective in shielding space radiation.

< Density of hydrogen in different materials ^[1] >

Materials	Number of Hydrogen Atoms per 1cm^3 ($\times 10^{22}$)	Density (g/cm^3)	Hydrogen molecule number per mass
H ₂ (liquid)	4.6	0.07	65.7
Water	6.7	0.997	6.72
LiH	5.9	0.820	7.19
ZrH ₂	7.3	5.6	1.30
HfH ₂	7.6	11.4	0.67
AlH ₃	8.9	1.49	5.97
TiH ₂	9.2	3.75	2.45
Polyethylene	7.9	0.93	8.49
Polystyrene	4.7	1.04	4.52
Polyimide	2.2	1.42	1.55
Polyamide	3.0	1.14	2.63
Cured Epoxy	5.1	1.18	4.32

- **UHMWPE fiber bulletproof performance**
- UHMWPE(Ultra-high-molecular-weight polyethylene) fiber is used as a body armor.
- The specific strength and specific modulus of UHMWPE fiber are 1.4 times that of Kevlar fiber.

1.6 Space Radiation Shielding + Hypervelocity Impact Shielding Structure

- 1) Characterization of space radiation shielding performance of UHMWPE
- 2) Performance evaluation of hypervelocity impact of UHMWPE fiber

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2.1 Experimental Schematic Diagram

2.2 Experiment Material Properties

Product name	Strength		Modulus		Elongation	Density	1 Layer area density	Denier	Melting point	Ends × Picks/cm
	g/d*	GPa	g/d*	GPa						
UHMWPE Spectra1000 ^[1]	35	3.00	1200	103	3.1	0.97	0.01094	375	148	13.7 × 13.7
Kevlar KM2 ^[2]	24	3.88	800	84.6	4.5	1.45	0.01882	600	450	12.7 × 12.7

(g/d*: Strength per fiber weight)

< Kevlar KM2 plain weave fabric >

< UHMWPE Spectra1000 plain weave fabric >

[1] Kurtz, Steven M, The UHMWPE handbook: ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene in total joint replacement, Academic Press, 2004, pp. 94-102.

[2] R. Destefanis, E. Amerio, M. Briccarello, 2010, SPACE ENVIRONMENT CHARACTERISATION OF KEVLAR®: GOOD FOR BULLETS, DEBRIS AND RADIATION TOO, International Symposium on Materials in a Space Environment

2.3 Experiment methods

Proton irradiation test:

< KIRAMS MC-50 Proton Accelerator >

Space Radiation Characteristics of UHMWPE

2.4 Proton Irradiation Experiment Results

Proton irradiation energy	Material	Number of layers	Shielded area density (g/cm^2)	Weight % over UHMWPE
27.5MeV	UHMWPE	69 ~ 70	0.7568	100.0%
	Kevlar	48 ~ 49	0.9216	121.8%
	Al6061-T6	t = 3.9 mm	1.0568	139.6%
	CFRP M55J/M18*	64 ~ 80	0.9456	124.9%
	Nextel AF-62*	12 ~ 13	1.339	176.9%

CFRPM55J/M18*: 16 layers : 0.2364 g/cm^2
Nextel AF-62*: 1 layer: 0.103 g/cm^2

[1]Jang, T.S., Rhee, J., Seo, J.K., Cha, W.H., "Study on Proton Shielding Effectiveness of Lightweight Polyethylene Composite for Space Radiation Shielding," Proceedings of the 2013 KSAS Fall Conference, pp.1172-1175, 2013.

2.5 Discussion of Proton Irradiation Experiment

- Proton shielding efficiency: UHMWPE > Kevlar > CFRP > Al > Nextel
- UHMWPE has a weight reduction effect of about 21.8% over Kevlar in 27.5 MeV proton shielding.
- According to the Bethe formula, UHMWPE is effective for heavy ion shielding.
- Replace conventional space materials with hydrogen-containing materials or UHMWPE.
→ Higher space radiation shielding performance.

< 27.5 MeV proton shielded areal density >

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3.1 Experimental Schematic Diagram

< Kevlar in impact chamber >

Absorbed impact energy?

< Before and after impact test of UHMWPE >

3.2 Experiment Method

- Accelerates 5.56mm diameter aluminum spheres up to 4 km/s.
- Velocity measurement with laser intervalometer and magnetic intervalometer.

< Light Gas Gun schematic diagram >

3.2 Experiment Method(2)

- At 60°C, UHMWPE mechanical properties are expected to decrease by 20%^[3].
- This change in behaviour is most probably due to the solid phase change from orthorhombic to hexagonal as described by B. Dessain^[3].
- Maximum temperature after MLI is below 50°C^{[1][2]}.

< UHMWPE temperature effect ^[1] >

Relative to 23°C	-60°C	+23°C	+60°C	+100°C
Tensile strength	110%	100%	80%	55%
Tensile modulus	110%	100%	85%	60%
Elongation at break	90%	100%	100%	105%

< Temperature condition^[2] >

< UHMWPE heating temperature setup >

	Center	Corner	Hot-wire
Experiment temperature	46 ~ 48°C	52 ~ 56°C	86 ~ 89°C

< High temperature impact test setting >

[1] MariaCristina Tosi and Luca Tentoni, ATV Thermal Control System, 34th ICES(724), 2004.

[2] Macdonald, Malcolm, and Viorel Badescu, eds. *The International Handbook of Space Technology*. Springer, 2014.

[3] B. Dessain, et al., "Solid phase change controlling the tensile and creep behaviour of gel-spun high-modulus polyethylene fibres," *J. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 27, no. 16, pp. 4515-4522, 1992.

3.3 High Temperature Impact Experiment Results

Kevlar 6 layers: 0.1129g/cm²

UHMWPE 10 layers: 0.1094g/cm²

UHMWPE at high temperature

Low velocity impact test	Kevlar	UHMWPE	UHMWPE at high TEMP.
$V_{initial}$	0.483 km/s	0.492 km/s	0.488 km/s
$V_{residual}$	0.305 km/s	0.315 km/s	0.346 km/s
$E_{absorbed} = \frac{1}{2}m(V_{initial}^2 - V_{residual}^2)$	0.01772 kJ	0.01792 kJ	0.01486 kJ
$E_{specific\ absorbed} = \frac{E_{absorbed}}{\text{Area density}}$	0.1569 kJ* cm ² /g	0.1638 kJ* cm ² /g	0.1358 kJ* cm ² /g
$E_{specific\ absorbed}$ % over Kevlar	95.8%	100.0%	82.9%

Hypervelocity impact test	Kevlar	UHMWPE	UHMWPE at high TEMP.
$V_{initial}$	3.236 km/s	3.262 km/s	3.206 km/s
$V_{residual}$	2.989 km/s	3.022 km/s	2.972 km/s
$E_{absorbed} = \frac{1}{2}m(V_{initial}^2 - V_{residual}^2)$	0.1929 kJ	0.1892 kJ	0.1814 kJ
$E_{specific\ absorbed} = \frac{E_{absorbed}}{\text{Area density}}$	1.708 kJ* cm ² /g	1.729 kJ* cm ² /g	1.658 kJ* cm ² /g
$E_{specific\ absorbed}$ % over Kevlar	98.8%	100.0%	95.9%

3.5 Discussion of Energy Absorption Experiment

- Energy absorption performance: UHMWPE > Kevlar > UHMWPE at high temperature
- Reduced performance difference between high temperature UHMWPE and Kevlar in hypervelocity region.
- Temperature effect of UHMWPE decreases in hypervelocity region.

< Specific absorbed energy test results >

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■ Space radiation shielding

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■ Space debris shielding

- Energy absorption performance: UHMWPE > Kevlar > UHMWPE at high temperature.
- Reduced performance difference in hypervelocity region.
- High temperature property lowering effect of UHMWPE decreases in hypervelocity region.

Space radiation shielding

Space debris shielding

UHMWPE is a good material for space radiation and space debris shielding.

**THANK
YOU FOR
LISTENING
ANY
QUESTION**